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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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MARKETING AS A DECISIVE ELEMENT IN THE SUCCESSFUL INTRODUCTION OF INNOVATIVE PRODUCTS TO THE MARKET.

Davlyatova Gulnara

Fergana State Technical University, associate professor
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2421-3345

Abstract. Nowadays, the main regularity of social development is the innovative renewal of the world economy, the transition to the so-called "new knowledge-based economy", the hallmark of which is the accelerated development of economic activity. Modern society is rapidly evolving in the direction of postindustrial, while the transformations that are taking place are so radical that we can talk about a paradigm shift in economic development. In the new economy, enterprises that produce innovative products are becoming key. However, practical experience indicates a high degree of risk of launching innovative products on the market: on average, about a third of new products are defeated and bring only losses instead of profits. Thus, marketing support for the creation of new products becomes one of the most important problems of an innovative company. This article discusses the importance of marketing research in introducing innovative products to the market, features of the market for innovative products, the effectiveness of marketing activities and features of marketing innovation.

Keywords: effectiveness of marketing activities, factors of success of a new product, market of innovative products, marketing of innovations.

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi kunda ijtimoiy rivojlanishning asosiy muntazamligi jahon iqtisodiyotining innovatsion yangilanishi, "yangi bilimga asoslangan iqtisodiyot" deb ataladigan iqtisodiyotga o'tishdir, uning asosiy belgisi iqtisodiy faoliyatning jadal rivojlanishidir. Zamonaviy jamiyat postindustrial yo'nalishda tez rivojlanmoqda, shu bilan birga sodir bo'layotgan o'zgarishlar shunchalik radikalki, biz iqtisodiy rivojlanishda paradigma o'zgarishi haqida gapirishimiz mumkin. Yangi iqtisodiyotda innovatsion mahsulotlar ishlab chiqaradigan korxonalar asosiy o'rinni egallamoqda. Biroq, amaliy tajriba bozorga innovatsion mahsulotlarni chiqarish xavfi yuqori ekanligini ko'rsatadi: o'rtacha hisobda yangi mahsulotlarning uchdan bir qismi mag'lubiyatga uchraydi va foyda o'rniga faqat zarar keltiradi. Shunday qilib, yangi mahsulotlarni yaratish uchun marketing yordami innovatsion kompaniyaning eng muhim muammolaridan biriga aylanadi. Ushbu maqolada bozorga innovatsion mahsulotlarni kiritishda marketing tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati, innovatsion mahsulotlar bozorining xususiyatlari, marketing faoliyatining samaradorligi va marketing innovatsiyalarining xususiyatlari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: marketing faoliyatining samaradorligi, yangi mahsulotning muvaffaqiyat omillari, innovatsion mahsulotlar bozori, innovatsiyalar marketingi.

Аннотация. Настоящее время, главной закономерностью общественного развития является инновационное обновление мировой экономики, переход к так называемой «новой экономике, основанной на знаниях», отличительной чертой которой является ускоренное развитие хозяйственной деятельности. Современное общество быстро эволюционирует в направлении постиндустриального, при этом происходящие трансформации носят столь радикальный характер, что можно говорить о смене парадигмы экономического развития. В новой экономике ключевыми становятся предприятия, которые производят инновационные продукты. Однако практический опыт свидетельствует о высокой степени риска выведения на рынок именно инновационных продуктов: в среднем около трети новых товаров терпят поражение и вместо прибылей приносят одни убытки. Таким образом маркетинговое сопровождение создания новых продуктов становится одной из важнейших проблем инновационной компании. В данной статье рассматривается значительность маркетинговых исследований в выведение инновационных продуктов на рынок, особенности рынка инновационных продуктов, эффективность маркетинговых мероприятий и особенности маркетинга инноваций.

Ключевые слова: факторы успешности нового товара, эффективность маркетинговых мероприятий, рынок инновационных товаров, маркетинг инноваций.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that modernization of the economy is the main and important condition for innovative development of the country. Nowadays, at a time when stabilization of the Republic of Uzbekistan is prevailing, it is difficult to achieve the diffusion of innovations, that is the introduction and rapid spread of new ideas, developments and technologies, without deep modernization of the economy. This will require, first of all, the integration of education, science and industry, as well as the introduction of a number of specific technical solutions that will facilitate the creation of new industries that will encourage the creation of new companies that will increase the demand for innovative products [2]. Today one of the most pressing issues facing the national economy is to achieve innovative development of the country in the short term. Otherwise, it is clear that it will be difficult to get a place in the ranks of developed countries for Uzbekistan. One of the main tasks for the positive solution of this issue is the implementation of comprehensive reforms. The Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a governmental agency which administrates implementation of a single state policy in the field of innovation and scientific and technological development of the country, aimed at comprehensive development of society and state life and increasing the intellectual and technological potential of the country. Innovation development is a systematic process, which involves the implementation of clearly defined measures according to the plan, that is, in a strategic way. In this regard, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018 No PD-5544, the strategy of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan during 2019 and 2021, the “road map” on its implementation, the confirmation of the indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan for innovative development until 2030 have been essential. The main purpose of the strategy is the development of human capital as the main factor determining the level of competitiveness of the country in the international arena and the development of innovation, and one of the important objectives of the strategy is the entry of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the ranks of 50 advanced countries of the world in terms of the Global Innovation Index ranking until 2030.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Initially, it is desirable to introduce clarification to the concept of innovation. In the era of economic globalization, innovative ways of organizing the system of all levels are crucial in the formation of a new model of economic growth. At the same time, the main tool of competition is not the possession of capital resources and material values, but the ability to develop and implement innovations. In this regard, the growing interest in the problem of innovative development on the part of both government agencies and businesses is obvious.

The first most complete description of innovation processes was introduced by the Austrian scientist J. Schumpeter in the work “Theory of economic development” published in 1911. According to J. Schumpeter, “innovation is a source of profit.” profit is essentially the result of performing new combinations”, “without development there is no profit, without profit there is no development» [6].

A. B. Titov considers innovations (innovation) as the final result of the creation and development (implementation) of a fundamentally new or modified tool (innovation) that meets specific social needs and gives a number of effects (economic, scientific, technical, social, environmental) [7].

In our opinion, the essence of innovation should be defined as the final result of a synergistic interaction of research and scientific and technical activities aimed at improving the technical level, as well as the release of new high-performance products and bringing economic, social, environmental, scientific and technical or other type of effect.

Nowadays, the market is dominated by fierce competition between enterprises, and to win in it, companies need to put a lot of effort. Therefore, innovation is one of the main factors of success in market conditions. It is innovation that gives companies the opportunity to create competitive advantages and successfully operate in the market in a highly competitive environment. In order to achieve this, businesses need to implement innovative transformations in a timely manner, identify new markets, and predict consumer preferences as quickly as possible.

It is innovation that helps ensure that a newly produced product has the necessary benefits for consumers that distinguish it from competitors' products, as well as protection from copying by competitors. Accordingly, the main condition for the introduction of any innovation at the present time is marketing research and technologies that identify the needs of consumers. Therefore, marketing is the most important component of the innovation management process of an enterprise that seeks to offer and implement a new product on the market.

As L. Ronald Hubbard notes, marketing helps prepare a product, deliver it to the market, and place it there in a way that achieves the highest possible sales and the highest possible response. Marketing allows you to research the needs of the market for innovations, generate demand for new technologies, analyze the company's capabilities, identify the needs of customers and offer the innovative product that will be in demand by the market.

By combining the concepts of “marketing” and “innovation” through the application of marketing research at all stages of creating an innovative product, it is possible to derive such a definition as “innovative marketing”.

From our point of view, the main problems of innovative process in Uzbekistan are largely related to the insufficient development of marketing in scientific-technical organizations and innovative enterprises. One of the most important problems of an innovative company is marketing support for the creation of new products. Practical experience indicates that there is a high risk of introducing innovative products to the market: on average, about a third of new products fail and bring only losses instead of profits.

The specifics of introducing new products to the market are related both to the specifics of the products themselves and to the specifics of the market. Generally, the following fail when entering the market:

- 25-27% of industrial goods;
- 33-35% of personal consumption goods;
- 28% expansion of the existing range;
- 30% of brand innovations;
- 45% of new products themselves.

As it can be noticed, the market of consumer commodities is more risky, due to the higher level of competition and the specific behavior of consumers in this segment. Additionally, these figures demonstrate a higher level of risk when introducing fundamentally new products to the market, which can often be attributed to the so-called breakthrough innovations. Among the reasons for the failure of new products, the following factors are usually identified: insufficient market analysis, product defects, lack of effective marketing measures, excessively high costs, actions of competitors, lack of support for bringing the product to market, production problems [3].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A systematic approach, generalization and synthesis methods are effectively and appropriately used in the article.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The relationship between the risks of innovative process and the level of marketing development in the company is clearly visible if look at the stages of the innovation project: 6 stages of the 14 stages listed below are directly related to the effectiveness of marketing activities carried out by the innovator/innovative company.

- search for new ideas
- preliminary market assessment
- the selection of the “right” ideas
- preliminary technical evaluation of the product
- detailed market research
- economic analysis (financial analysis)
- development of a new product concept (production of a prototype)
- technical testing of the product
- testing by consumers
- experienced sales
- experienced production
- economic analysis (clarification of financial indicators)
- launch production
- bringing the product to market

In other words, the factors of the success of a new product are:

- the superiority of the product over its competitors (distinctive properties that contribute to a better perception by consumers);
- marketing know-how of the company (understanding the behavior of customers, the pace of adoption of new products and the size of the potential market);
- existence of the technological know-how which is protected by a patent or trade secret regime.

As it is seen, commercial success cannot be ensured only by obtaining technological advantage. Thus, any innovator or innovative company will sooner or later have to think about marketing factors.

Innovative products form a specific market for high-tech and scientific-technical products. Its features in comparison with the market of “traditional” goods are diverse and affect all aspects of the relationship between the seller and the buyer, requiring, accordingly, their reflection in the marketing policy of the company. Among the features of this market, the following should be highlighted:

- particular qualities of the product itself (uniqueness; sometimes technological complexity; high costs for its production at the first stages);
- the novelty of the market for the firm (especially for a small innovative company that is at the start-up stage);
- unknown product (and sometimes manufacturer) for the market;
- unpredictability of consumer behavior;
- low elasticity of demand from the price, so, as a result, a limited impact of pricing policy on sales volumes;
- small market capacity (especially for high-tech industrial products);
- lack of direct competitors at the initial stages (due to the monopoly on intellectual property);
- achievements of the company's employees in the theoretical field with a well-constructed policy which can significantly raise the company's rating among consumers;
- dependence of sales of innovative products on the level of innovative potential of the consumer: many pioneer innovations are difficult to sell due to the general technological backwardness of a number of sales markets [4].

The problems of bringing innovative products to the market that are unfamiliar to the consumer are primarily associated with the risk of unpredictability of the reaction of buyers. This is typical for companies operating in any industry, but for the market of high-tech products, where the speed of product updates is particularly high, this is especially relevant. An innovative product can "fail" without proper consumer training, without an elaborated strategy for bringing this product to market.

As mentioned above, the specifics of the innovation market determine the features of innovation marketing, which is appeared in the following:

- the necessity of research and study potential consumers in several industries at once, since quite often the results of scientific and technical development have intersectoral character;
- selling innovative products requires a long and consistent advertising campaign, so as the buyer must "Mature": they need to be explained in detail the meaning and benefits of innovation, otherwise they will not buy this product, because they are not familiar with it;
- innovative products should not only meet qualitatively new needs or old needs in a qualitatively new way, but also provide additional advantages that consumers can understand in comparison with existing analogues and substitutes;
- when promoting complex scientific and technical products on the market, it should be focused on an experienced, so-called the "collective" consumer ("purchasing center", which can include employees from various departments – from purchasing to production);
- sales of innovative products require lengthy negotiations, since high-tech products are pre-selected in both the production and consumer markets, and therefore purchases are made through multiple comparisons and discussions with experts;
- very often, the technical complexity of innovative products implies the organization of a good after-sales service: in other words, no service - no commercial success of the new product. An example is the promotion of hybrid cars to the market, the spread of which was hindered not only by their price, but also by insufficient development at the first stage of their maintenance infrastructure;
- the image of an innovative company is significantly influenced by the results of fundamental research of its employees. In addition, conferences, scientific forums, and other forms of communication in the professional community can serve as marketing communication channels for innovative businesses;
- the complexity of an innovative product creates special prerequisites for the formation of a so-called "whole product", where all its real and potential advantages are considered in a complex.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

All the factors listed above prove the importance of the marketing complex for companies in the innovation sphere. Most of these companies should be classified as small and medium-sized enterprises, so their main characteristics are the small size of the company (including the number of employees) and limited resources. In this regard, marketing has its own characteristics, as mentioned above. There are many definitions of marketing, but the definition given in the small business marketing Guide seems to be the most appropriate for an innovative business.

Marketing includes all the functions of satisfying the needs of the consumer by promoting the right product from the manufacturer to the right consumer at the right price in the right place, at the right time and with the right communication with the consumer.

In other words, the combination of these six "right" leads to customer satisfaction and successful effective marketing.

In our opinion, in modern conditions, marketing should solve the following tasks:

- discover the real needs of real consumers of new products and services;
- satisfy these needs by bringing the right product to market, at the right price, in the right place, at the right time;
- inform the consumer about the new product by using the right advertising company, using the right information channels.

Furthermore, it is essential to note that high-quality marketing research of the innovation market allows to carry out effective innovative activities in the future that meet the requirements and needs of the market. Before starting to develop a new product, the organization needs to determine who is the target audience of an innovative product, and what consumer needs it will meet. This approach contributes to the correct promotion and positioning of a new product (service, technology) on the market.

A set of marketing measures should be aimed at convincing consumers that this product is ideal for them at the present time. That is, the fact that an innovative product is able to meet their specific needs. Before introducing an innovative product to the market, the company will have to conduct trial marketing by testing the product, making trial sales, participating in competitions, exhibitions, and fairs.

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